

SOCIAL SCIENCES

CREATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF DIGITAL RESOURCES OF SCIENTIFIC NATIONAL LIBRARIES

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Abstract

The emergence and improvement of new forms and methods of presenting information provide an impetus for the development of scientific and sociocultural field of society; determine the trends in the development of social communications, domestic and global information space. The classification of modern types, forms and methods of creating digital resources allows us to distinguish different methods of their preparation and outline the circle of experts with a specialty in creating specific types of resources, study the special needs of users, ways to ensure the development of society, and also develop such a direction of integration of activities of humanities scholars and information technology specialists – as Digital Humanities.

Keywords: digitalization of scientific library, scientific and informational activities of libraries; Digital Humanities.

The current stage of development of library functions, in particular scientific and informational ones, is clearly related to the digital transformation of the scientific library activity. The leading role of the scientific library in the organization and implementation of scientific and information activities in present-day Ukraine directly follows from the legislative framework. In particular, the Law of Ukraine “On Scientific and Technical Information” states, “Scientific and information activities are a set of actions aimed at meeting the needs of citizens, legal entities and the state in scientific and technical information, which consists in its collection, analytical and synthetic processing, documentation, storage, search and dissemination” (*the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1993*). Today's libraries develop and provide users with virtual or traditional access to verified information in the desired form. Libraries issue many scientific and information publications, which appear on the pages of websites and testify to the intense activity of the scientific libraries of the NAS of Ukraine. However, the main attention in the development of the main information function of libraries – acquisition, systematization of information sources, organization of storage and provision of immediate access today is focused on the creation of electronic resources.

The digitalization of society has led to the emergence of new types of information services for science and culture and the systematic publication of research results, as well as interactive forms of scientific communication. Accordingly, libraries have expanded their activities in the field of scientific resource formation and management, the development of new forms and methods of resource use by expanding communication capabilities for the introduction of knowledge into various areas of science, culture, education and by clarifying the targeting of information. The entire information and technological system of organizing a multi-faceted library system is being reviewed to support scientific research, improve the structure of scientific information, create targeted databases, provide services to a wide range of users, as well as the relevant principles

of scientific research and publishing activities, taking into account the fundamental changes that have taken place in current digital scientific communication.

The two largest scientific libraries, namely the national libraries within the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine – the Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine (VNLU, Kyiv) and the V. Stefanyk National Scientific Library of Ukraine in Lviv are, without a doubt, the leading libraries in the Ukrainian library environment in all the above areas. These were the projects implemented by their scientific teams aimed at creating a network of electronic resources that became the basis for the classification of modern types, forms and methods of creating digital resources presented later in this paper. The historiographical basis for the analysis were the papers of modern librarians, who, firstly, reveal dealing with funds as a historical and cultural heritage and a scientific resource [2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7]; secondly, they highlight library digital projects, the features of their creation, curatorship and support [1; 8; 9; 10], and, thirdly, generalize the library component in up-to-date digital humanities [11].

Therefore, based on the analyzed library digital projects, the structure of resources of national scientific libraries at the highest level of classification can be presented as follows:

1. Scientific search and scientific reference electronic systems (electronic catalogs and bibliographic databases), which significantly increase the efficiency of providing the scientific community and government agencies with bibliographic, bibliometric, and scientometric information at various levels of information representation. This is one of many new areas of resources being prepared by academic libraries.

2. Full-text resources and databases of scientific information, structured according to certain principles, which replenish the global information space of scientific knowledge and expand the scope of active use of the scientific potential of the state. One of the directions is the integration of information from these databases into the European system of open science, the project

of which is being developed at the NAS of Ukraine and other institutions, in particular, university education.

3. Organization of **digital collections of library cultural heritage**, which is recognized as the national cultural heritage of Ukraine, as well as the creation of a digital fund of insurance copies, which will ensure the formation of a new cultural space of Ukraine, which actively influences the formation and preservation of the mentality of modern society during wartime and the preservation of information for future generations. Providing digital full-text copies as an insurance resource and a new type of service for users of cultural heritage is one of the crucial tasks today. Currently, active research and creation of cultural heritage resources are underway in Ukraine in the national libraries of the NAS of Ukraine, which is reflected in numerous papers and monographic theses by employees of the Institute of Information Technologies of the Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine.

This structure has developed subsystems of digital resources aimed at fulfilling the functions of libraries and society's orders in relevant information.

One of the new methodological transformations should be considered the integration of the work of library and research fellows with specialists in the field of information technology in joint work with thematic full-text resources, the development of the structure of knowledge and its information representation thanks to digital technologies. We are talking about Digital Humanities – one of the new directions of scientific and information work, which allows us to withstand the challenges of today for the further existence of libraries in an active information space.

Library specialists provide complex functional responsibilities at the expert level related to the implementation of digital projects. This primarily concerns the participation of scientific libraries in digital socio-humanitarian projects related to the creation of resources of national memory and cultural heritage. Joint teams of such specialists allow for the most effective provision of verified information based on scientific expertise of cultural heritage for its storage, use and full perception in the sociocultural space.

Contemporary libraries provide users with virtual or traditional access to verified information in the desired form. The digitalization of society has led to the emergence of new types of information services for science and the systematic publication of research results and interactive forms of scientific communication, including in a popular science form in the media space. Libraries have accordingly expanded their activities in the field of scientific resource formation and management, new forms and methods of resource use, expansion of communication opportunities for the introduction of knowledge into various areas of science, culture, and education.

The accumulated experience of implementing large-scale projects on digitizing library collections and creating resources for modern science indicates the need for legislative overcoming the limitation of their effectiveness by law on the protection of copyrights for modern works.

The contemporary information society causes significant changes in the field of scientific communication and scientific and information activities of scientific libraries, including in the sociocultural field. A significant expansion of the possibilities of information exchanges between the entities of science and culture as an innovative process due to the development of communication technology not only accelerates the process of dissemination of scientific information, but also contributes to the emergence of new types and forms and means of communication in the scientific space, the use of information content expands the possibilities for development not only of science and culture, but also of society in general. The rapid growth of information volumes due to the emergence and expansion of the digital information space and the significant simplification of the everyday use of state-of-the-art technology for creating and distributing data have confirmed the ever-growing role of libraries as versatile, professional institutions capable of meeting the needs of society in verified information in the most efficient and convenient way. This is the issue of processing information and organizing access to it.

An important phenomenon of the use of digital technology and communications by libraries in the field of science and culture is that the cultural space itself, its content and communication capabilities, are radically changing, filling it with new systematized information that appears due to studying the retrospective funds by libraries that have accumulated historically and are currently insufficiently introduced into scientific and cultural circulation. This information contributes to a significant replenishment with up-to-date information about the development of science, culture and education of the historical past, about historical events, prominent representatives, the development of social structures, etc., which were hushed up or distorted in previous years. Replenishment with reliable information is of extreme importance in the context of changes in the state priorities of Ukraine in the formation of the national and civilizational mentality of ordinary citizens, public consciousness, as well as use in specific scientific and educational work.

This work requires libraries to improve systematically, as they are constantly replenishing their funds with new information through constant acquisition of archival funds, manuscript heritage, and modern scientific, artistic, political, and economic publications, newspapers and magazines, and other socially significant information. The scientific knowledge, the economic and political sphere of society, the technological development of society are being improved, and the structure of the sociocultural space, which also receives meaningful development, improves as well. Scientific libraries form collections and electronic resources in all fields of knowledge. Library types, forms and methods of information also acquire the opportunity to present, among other things, their scientific achievements, popularize their activities, expand, and deepen cultural exchanges of libraries with entities of cultural activity both within the state and outside it.

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